

eLTER stakeholder screening

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Preface

eLTER is a pan-European distributed research infrastructure (RI), with a consolidated strategic plan outlining the scientific and strategic objectives at the European scale. Due to the high scientific and societal relevance of the RI's strategic objectives, and because of its core commitment to stakeholder integration throughout all of its activities, eLTER RI engages in a diverse array of stakeholders, both internal and external and both academic and non-academic. These stakeholders have many different needs and requirements for assuring successful integration and interactions. Some of these relationships have been existing for decades, forming a rich history of collaboration, while some are only now emerging or are being planned in the course of implementing the eLTER Research Infrastructure.

Reflecting the high priority of stakeholder interactions, the eLTER Preparatory Phase Project (eLTER PPP) and the Advanced Communities Project (eLTER PLUS) both have tasks and deliverables related to mapping, engaging and activating the stakeholder relationships.

Bullet lists:

- PPP D1.3 (Mirtl et al. 2021) on European and global partnerships, but with a focus creating RI level working and strategic partnerships with peer RIs and networks in Europe and globally.
- PLUS D2.1 eLTER stakeholder screening (this deliverable): Exploring and mapping the whole stakeholder landscape and focussing on the immediate eLTER bottom-up community and scientific networks with lesser focus on formal aspects at European level decision making (this is an integral part of the eLTER PPP activities).
- PPP 7.1 eLTER Stakeholder landscape analysis (Barov et al. 2021): Identified 7 priority stakeholder categories in a broad consultation and analysis to be used in the eLTER ESFRI process and as a key reference across both projects, eLTER related activities and services development. The focus of this report is on user needs of about 40 user groups assigned to the 7 categories.

The eLTER PLUS D2.1 systematically utilises the results from this comprehensive stakeholders/users screening. An inherent component of eLTER PLUS implementation is the dynamic and interactive prioritization and further development of these diverse relationships to (1) maximize the relevance and usage of eLTER services or (2) enable smooth complementarities, collaboration, co-design and co-development.

Main text (Calibri point 11; single line spacing; full justification; 1 line spacing between paragraphs; no other spacing before or after paragraphs)

Summary

This Deliverable uses the stakeholder categorization from the work done in eLTER PLUS WP2 and the Preparatory Phase Project WP1.3 and WP7.1, and focuses on characterizing three out of seven stakeholder categories, i) Internal stakeholders with the current priority target groups (Site and Platform Coordinators, National Coordinators), ii) Researchers and scientific stakeholders, and iii) Peers in environmental research and observation (incl. environmental RIs). This Deliverable explains the relationship with these stakeholders and contributes to the decisions on formal priority interactions to be executed through eLTER PPP in the eLTER Interim Council. It also describes the current status of their engagement and ongoing and planned interactions with these stakeholders in the eLTER ESFRI process.

The deliverable will be updated and amended with additional information regarding interactions and engagement over the duration of the project, according to the timing of dedicated tasks (e.g. WP2.3 and WP2.4) and the advancements of the eLTER ESFRI process.

1 Introduction & structure

*“eLTER catalyzes scientific discovery and insights through its state-of-the-art research infrastructure, collaborative working culture, and transdisciplinary expertise”
--- eLTER RI Strategic Plan, Vision. May 2021*

The history of eLTER RI (the Integrated European Long-Term Ecosystem, critical zone and socio-ecological Research Infrastructure) is closely connected to the bottom-up network of national LTER networks (member networks of the global ILTER) in Europe and the foundation of a formal European regional group of ILTER (“LTER-Europe”) in 2007. Already in 2001, the European Environmental Agency (EEA) had advocated for such a European network at an international LTER conference in London, and the first LTER conference gathering all European LTER initiatives was held in 2003 (Mirtl, 2013). The European Community funded “Network of Excellence” project ALTER-Net provided a crucial push towards the official establishment of LTER Europe (Mirtl et al. 2018). The long history has manifested itself as gradually intensifying collaboration in research and monitoring, and the creation of many joint national and international projects among the partners. The community has expanded over the decades and led to the current continent-wide coverage of 26 national LTER networks with ~500 LTER sites and ~50 LTER platforms.

In accordance with its desire to pursue a more formal and sustainable structure, the European LTER community applied successfully for the position in the European Strategy Forum for Research Infrastructures (ESFRI) Roadmap in 2018. The fundamental backbones for the distributed developing eLTER RI are (1) well-functioning sites and platforms, (2) the research community exploiting the services, knowledge, and facilities at the sites and platforms, (3) the efficient interaction and fruitful collaboration between different research infrastructures co-located in many of the sites and (4) the decision making level of country representatives. Importantly, full realization of the potential of these backbones depends on engaging multiple stakeholder groups inside and outside of the eLTER RI.

The recently drafted eLTER RI Strategic Plan (Nikolaidis, et al., 2021) derives strategic goals and objectives from eLTER’s vision and mission. Several of these goals emphasize the importance of a well-structured and targeted stakeholder engagement:

- Objective A1: Enable scientific collaboration of multiple research communities across scales and disciplines.
- Objective A2: Attract excellent science to the eLTER facilities for research.
- Objective A4d: Enable break-through advancements in response to Research Challenges addressed by eLTER RI, [emphasizing, among others] sustainable use of resources... with input from researchers representing diverse disciplinary expertise and non-academic stakeholders.
- Objective B3: Nurture technological, methodological and operational innovation... and invest in capacity building and knowledge transfer across all stakeholders for establishing new technologies.
- Objective B5: Establish strategic partnerships to promote collaboration and co-location of in-situ facilities with existing and emerging environmental monitoring networks and research infrastructures and initiatives in Europe and globally.
- Objective C1: Provide services to a broad range of 7 stakeholder (user) categories, comprising external stakeholder categories like scientists, funding agencies, peer RIs, policy decision makers, industry, and the general public, while internal users are site-based researchers, site managers, data managers, and internal eLTER service providers.
- Objective C2a: Combine a range of services from the RI and beyond to deliver tailored thematic service packages to support eLTER stakeholders...[including] services designed within the RI to respond to its stakeholder requirements.
- Objective D2: Establish a working culture specializing in inter- and transdisciplinary approaches [by developing]... novel tools for attracting and communicating with diverse stakeholder communities to convey scientific information and facilitate a productive and pluralistic multi-directional knowledge exchange.

- Objective D3: eLTER scientists will undergo transversal and transdisciplinary training to develop a broad range of capacities necessary for working with stakeholders, including stakeholder engagement, citizen science, recognizing and confronting biases, and training for working across disciplinary boundaries.

Another key reference for this report is the stakeholder analysis (Barov et al 2021, eLTER PPP, D7.1). All stakeholder groups were clustered in 7 stakeholder categories (the focus groups of this deliverable are underlined):

- Science & researchers
- Funders of research & RIs
- Decision makers
- Peers in research and observation
- Internal stakeholders
- Business & industry
- Civil society & public

The eLTER strategic goals and objectives are currently being operationalized in the eLTER PLUS Advanced Communities Project. The main aims of the eLTER PLUS are to further open and expand the site and platform network, engage current and new users from both academia and other stakeholder groups, and pilot and integrate the operations of eLTER to advance cross-disciplinary and transdisciplinary research on ecosystems and critical zone. eLTER PLUS aims at providing European researchers and wider stakeholder communities with targeted and efficient services, integrated and harmonised methods and data management, and improved capacities of, and access to, existing long-term ecological research observatories for both scientific advancement and policy support. Among the key expected impacts of eLTER PLUS is an improvement in the users' knowledge level and capacities, and enhanced engagement to and appreciation of the developing RI. This is expected to increase the number and diversity of users and strengthen the eLTER community leadership in environmental research in Europe and globally.

eLTER RI will provide a high-quality service portfolio for a large variety of stakeholders. To ensure success in the scientific objectives, as well as in providing input to the eLTER ESFRI process, the partners in the project collaborate and co-design the future services with a large and diverse group of stakeholders at all stages: in framing and iterating research questions and standard observations, gathering data, conducting joint case studies and testing co-location, making syntheses, applying new technologies, as well as disseminating results to a wide range of fora.

In summary, stakeholder integration is a crucial component of eLTER RI and permeates all of its activities in order to assure both scientific and social-policy relevance and to fulfill the strategic objectives of the RI.

The objective of eLTER PLUS WP2, task 2.1 was to enable prioritization of network activities by first quantitatively mapping the stakeholder landscape by employing multiple methodologies to define current and potential stakeholders for engagement. In order to address these objectives, we introduce two methods for the stakeholder screening and characterize three priority stakeholder categories derived from these screenings. This selection is analysed in detail and steps for their engagement during the project duration and beyond are elaborated.

2 Methods

2.1 Stakeholder analysis and selection of stakeholders for this deliverable

To provide a quantitative overview across all sectors and help structuring all stakeholder-targeted activities of the entire eLTER ESFRI process, a full stakeholder analysis was performed by eLTER PPP WP7.1 (Barov et al. 2021). The stakeholders were clustered in 7 stakeholder categories comprising more specific stakeholder groups (in total about 40) (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Graphical overview of stakeholder categories and groups therein

Short description of the stakeholder categories and comprised groups (Barov et al 2021):

- **Researchers and science stakeholders**, who are interested in the services (e.g. sites, data, training) of the RI. This ranges from, for example, individual scientists, research organisations, research networks focusing on pertinent science initiatives at the international level.
- **Peers in environmental research and observation**, like related monitoring and observation networks and organizations in-situ and remote (e.g. UNECE-Working Group on Effects, WMO, JRC, ESA/Copernicus, EIONET) or related research infrastructures in the environmental domain. Within this category, European scale e-infrastructure (e.g., LifeWatch) and e-infrastructure initiatives like the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) need to be taken into account as stakeholders interacting with the eLTER Information System as users.
- **Internal stakeholders**, such as the site and platform coordinators (SPC), the site and platform operating institutions or the National LTER networks coordination teams (NC).
- **Research and Research Infrastructure funders** ranging from national to European, as well as international, funding organisations which are important in the financing and sustainability of the research infrastructures.
- **Government and policy decision-makers** ranging from European policy makers, European agencies (executive bodies) in the realm of eLTER (e.g. EEA, JRC, contributors to monitoring & conservation directives), to national and regional authorities and policy makers, and the eLTER formal decision making body, the Interim Council (eLTER IC). Also global agencies and intergovernmental organisations are considered important stakeholders.
- **Business and industry**, which can utilize services of the eLTER RI or enable innovation and cooperation in terms of observation (e.g., sensors) or information management, as well as environmental (impact) consultants and spatial architects.
- **Civil society organisations and interested members of the public** ranging from Citizen Science organisations, environmental NGOs, land and forest owners' organisations, to the wider public.

In accordance with the eLTER projects priorities and timing of activities, this report focusses on the first three (underlined). Future versions of the report will iteratively cover other elements.

These are the main considerations behind the selection of stakeholder groups for the first project phase: Site and Platform Coordinators (internal stakeholders): The Site and Platform Coordinators (SPCs) were chosen because they are the national stakeholders in the distributed RI, who have already heavily invested in the potential LTER sites and will greatly influence the successful implementation of eLTER. They are potential backbone operators of the distributed RI.

- The National Coordinators (internal stakeholders): The national LTER networks are coordinated by one or a few National Coordinators (NCs) in each participating country. These persons are crucial in bidirectional information flow; both from the countries to the RI and vice versa. Up to now, all NCs are also the key contacts for the national ESFRI processes. They therefore have a pivotal role in the eLTER ESFRI process as a link between the SPCs, funding agencies and decision-making (Interim Council).
- Researchers and science stakeholders (both internal and external stakeholders): The research communities and individual researchers are the drivers and main end users of services provided by the eLTER RI. Hence, engagement with science stakeholders provides invaluable feedback for further outlining the value of these services for scientific excellence goals.
- Peers in environmental research and observation RIs (external stakeholders): eLTER is embedded in the landscape of environmental RIs in Europe and globally. The relationships require coordinated actions between the peer RIs and initiatives, and such interfaces are actively developed in eLTER PLUS.

We will outline, how these three groups relate to the decision making in Interim Council, but it is the eLTER PPP project, which is particularly tasked to manage the decision making process of the Interim Council.

2.2 Mindmapping for defining key stakeholder groups

Based on previous landscape analyses carried out in the context of the FP6 NoE Alter-Net, FP7 ExpEER and eLTER H2020 projects and with updates from 2020, the eLTER PLUS WP2.1 team produced a mindmap of eLTER's strategic environment, which was re-structured to fit the reference system of eLTER Stakeholders summarized in the previous chapter.

The purpose of this mindmap is (1) to comprehensively map not only current and future eLTER RI users (stakeholders), but all elements of the strategic environment, which eLTER needs to consider to specify its niche without collisions and prioritized collaborations, (2) to provide an overview of eLTER experts in charge is individual interfaces ("key accounts"), and (3) to visualize relevant formats and bodies for interactions.

In order to increase the completeness, the eLTER PLUS and PPP consortia were consulted in a dedicated session of the projects meeting on 8th April 2021 with a focus on identifying candidate key accounts, which are (through previous contacts or ongoing parallel activities) knowledgeable about or even actively themselves engaged in elements of eLTER's environment. Such knowledge or ongoing engagement provides a time and cost efficient opportunity to interact, which also builds on existing working relations, trust and access to information.

The figures below show the mindmap's legend (Figure 2) and versions of the mindmap with increasing levels of detail (Figures 3 and 4).

MindMap v29 new grouping

Figure 2. Mindmap legend: Dark green indicates actual components of eLTER or elements mainly organized by eLTER; light green with dark frame: names of key account candidates; red: priority formats end bodies for interactions; blue: major meetings; *Asterisks after the name of elements indicate compliant eLTER Stakeholder categories. Some of the main stakeholder categories are split into functional sub-groups

Figure 3. Mindmap of the eLTER environment: Levels 1-3

Figure 4. Mindmap of the eLTER environment: all details including the key accounts.

The mindmap reveals at one glance the current emphasis of interactions with peers in environmental monitoring, research and research infrastructures and a big number of experts engaged in related projects, networks and RIs. Reflecting an almost quantitative response of two big consortia and huge community, gaps in interactions with business and industry and the public are revealed at the same time. However, these gaps are covered by the eLTER PLUS DoW in WP1 tasks, which start from the third project year onwards.

3 Characterization and current engagement activities with the selected stakeholder groups

3.1 National eLTER stakeholders

3.1.1 LTER Site and Platform Coordinators (SPCs)

eLTER is a distributed Research Infrastructure (RI). In this context, “distributed” implies that the facilities and activities are hosted by >100 institutions in >20 countries across the European continent and even beyond. The ~500 LTER sites and ~50 LTER platforms registered and documented in globally used registry

operated by eLTER ([DEIMS-SDR](#)) are the backbone of these distributed activities. Each site and platform has a coordinator or coordinating team (“Site and Platform Coordinators”, SPC), overseeing and leading day-to-day activities, including maintenance and upgrading of observations, hosting visitors and uploading datasets for access by users and the wider community. These SPCs also guarantee the local strategic input to their respective national infrastructures. They are a diverse group, differing in scientific and disciplinary background, research and administrative experience, and other characteristics. The critical importance and mandate of the SPCs is well recognized across all countries participating in eLTER, even considering the many different titles that are used for them: Primary investigators (PIs), site managers, site coordinators, LTSER Platform managers, etc. The diversity of titles indicate that SPCs have multifaceted and diverse roles beyond only management and infrastructure leadership, often bridging into the science domain. Accordingly, their job profiles and terms of engagement are not necessarily very well defined. The roles may also vary across countries and institutions.

The eLTER PLUS WP2 and the eLTER PPP stakeholder analyses clearly showed that there is strong need to connect and engage SPCs through joint activities. Such activities are required to inform, as well as to fully engage, empower and activate them in the current and future development of eLTER RI. To meet this critical need, the eLTER PLUS project initiated a Site and Platforms Forum, the SPF. The SPF concept (Annex 1) was developed in the eLTER PLUS WP2.2, and discussed, further developed and agreed in WP- and project meetings in 2020–2021. It was decided to establish this body in a very early phase, and thus the first SPF meeting (attended by 250 SPCs from 23 countries, see Figure 5 for a gallery of photos taken by participants) was organized in January 2021 together with the WP2.1 networking team. Following this meeting, four topical working groups were launched to more directly and actively engage SPCs in strategically important questions and tasks. These groups were provided with a forum to inform their plans at the second SPF, September 28–29 (2nd reporting period). The working groups are led and governed by SPCs with diverse backgrounds and geographical affiliation and all of them have had several satellite meetings to plan activities and prioritize topics related to (1) governance, (2) data management, (3) information clusters and (4) training. These working groups are also in direct contact with the relevant eLTER PPP/PLUS WP and task leaders to secure direct linkages for harnessing ideas and inputs from this important group of stakeholders to related project activities and deliverables

To further cater to and visualize the diverse perspectives, needs and roles of SPCs, we worked as a group to generate and elaborate upon five fictional “personas” which were developed to illustrate the multifaceted SPC roles. In interactive sessions, we discussed opportunities, constraints and challenges based on these personas. This has been an appreciated tool for networking and for creating a collective sense of “we” in the eLTER SPC community.

Figure 5: Photos out of SPCs windows during the first SPF meeting in January 2021

SPCs also play an important role in the networking and relationships of eLTER with a wide range of stakeholder groups. This is due to a variety of possible linkages of the actual *in-situ* facilities, their operating institutions, the SPCs and entire local research teams:

1. **Co-location of RIs at sites:** more than one RI might be using a given site, which raises important strategic and logistical questions: How can RI specific design requirements be integrated without disturbing each other, but rather bringing an added value to the site operations? How can instrumentation be co-used and co-operated? What are proper co-management and co-funding models? Up to now, most of these questions were entirely left to be solved at the site- and institutional level. The SPCs' input is crucially important for elaborating strategic options at the RI-level, which are based on the experiences at sites in order to achieve feasible solutions. Therefore, the active SPC engagement is of high-level strategic relevance for a fruitful development of eLTER RI. SPCs will on the other hand also be users of strategic eLTER RI services related to strategy building and practical recommendations and guidelines on co-location and co-management in accordance with RI-RI collaboration agreements, substantively reducing the overall efforts in finding distributed solutions.
2. **Involvement in activities contributing to national, European and global environmental observation and data reporting:** many of the eLTER sites and eLTER platforms were originally established in other contexts and for other purposes than eLTER. Consequently, they do serve several purposes like forming part of national/European/global monitoring schemes like UNECE/CLRTAP/UNECE International Cooperative Programmes (Forest, Water, Integrated Monitoring, Vegetation), EMEP, WMO etc.. Most of these programmes are in continuous development and re-design. Site-level activities and integration are therefore important testbeds for strategic collaborations at the level of eLTER as a whole. Reversely, strategic collaboration decisions can be pilot-wise implemented at sites. Once more, SPCs do play a critical role both strategically and operationally.

- SPCs belong to the core of the eLTER testbed for services before Service Bundles are provided to larger communities outside eLTER. In this respect, SPCs represent an intermediate between “internal” and “external” stakeholders and users.

3.1.2 National Coordinators

The National LTER Coordinators (NCs) (coordinating national LTER networks) are crucial pivots and bridges between the European eLTER ESFRI process, eLTER PPP and eLTER PLUS and the existing national networks. Secondly, the NCs act as an important node to national stakeholders and funders. Thirdly, the national eLTER ESFRI processes are up to now also coordinated by the NCs (national consortia building, proposals for inclusion at the national RI roadmaps, decision making and needed inputs for the eLTER RI specification). The 26 countries currently having active national LTER networks are each coordinated by a scientifically merited NC working at a leading organization. The NCs have been forming a peer support team which has been engaged in the eLTER PLUS as beneficiaries for facilitating the bidirectional information flow. NCs are the links to the large user community of LTER Europe (several thousand experts working in LTER Sites and LTER Platforms) and are pivotal for consultations on key eLTER PLUS deliverables like the Standard Observations (eLTER PLUS WP3) and service components.

Figure 6. National Coordinators’ roles in the national eLTER ESFRI processes. Particularly the three lowest points are relevant activities where eLTER PLUS supports the NCs through its Work Packages. eLTER PPP is supporting the NCs particularly in their work with the Interim Council.

3.2. Researchers and Science stakeholders

The second stakeholder group selected from the stakeholder mapping is “Researchers and Scientific communities”. They constitute the key user group for all eLTER RI services and are also the key group in defining what kinds of services are needed and how they should be provided to benefit the high level scientific research. The key impact of eLTER PLUS is realized by strong commitment to transdisciplinary, impact-oriented research, integrating world-leading natural and socio-ecological science.

The large pool of engaged and potential researchers can be partially explained by the evolution of the eLTER RI. eLTER PLUS originates from a series of flagship projects in the field of ecosystem, critical zone and

socio-ecological research, including ALTER-Net (FP6), EnvEurope (Life+), EXPEER (FP7), and eLTER (H2020). Concretely, eLTER PLUS builds upon the existing LTER-Europe and Critical Zone networks, and it has a solid foundation in the long-term collaboration within and between the networks. These networks cover >500 in-situ research sites and platforms, encompassing the eco-climatological zones of continental Europe and beyond (e.g. Israel, French Guiana). Thus, eLTER RI's core of researchers spans across scores of countries and their national LTER networks. The reservoir of scientific stakeholders grows broader still, when considering our past and future collaborations with sister RIs in Europe and globally.

eLTER interacts with different scientific communities and learned societies that are organized in networks such as the soil science (ISMC), Hydrology (Young Hydrologic Society), climate and atmospheric sciences (GEWEX), the global network of critical zone observatories (CZEN) and the British Ecological Society (BES), the NATURA network, PECS in ICSU and others.

Our disciplinary breadth of expertise is another appeal for a large existing and potential scientific stakeholder community. The scientific basis of eLTER PLUS is in a well-established and integrated community of world leading researchers with a unique combination of expertise spanning biodiversity, biogeochemical and hydrological cycles, and socio-ecological sciences, all contributing to the whole system approach that will underpin the eLTER RI. eLTER's Science Case is supported through a Memorandum of Understanding (MoU) signed by 165 Research Performing Organisations (RPOs), including leading institutes in 28 countries.

eLTER PLUS addresses the Grand Challenges identified in the EU's 7th Environment Action Programme (e.g., Steffen et al., 2015) that are critical for the sustainable future of European societies. The project selected four thematic eLTER PLUS Research Challenges (RCs). These long-term eLTER RCs encompass the threats to terrestrial and freshwater biodiversity loss, impacts of climate change on food and fibre production, adverse impacts of changes in land use and land management, and security of water and soil resources, addressed under the conceptual framework of eLTER's Whole System Approach (Mirtl et al., 2018; Nikolaidis et al., 2021). The fact that none of them can be addressed in isolation emphasizes the crucial need for multi-disciplinary data with sufficiently large spatial and temporal coverage and a Whole System Approach as executed by eLTER PLUS.

The four Research Challenges in eLTER PLUS are:

- Biodiversity loss (RC1 BDL)
- Biogeochemical controls of ecosystem functions (RC2 BGC)
- Climate-water-food nexus (RC3 CWF)
- Socio-ecological systems (RC4 SES)

The four eLTER PLUS Research Challenges are addressed by respective Case studies at two scales (WP8 site scale and WP9 pan-European scale). The research in RCs is performed by researchers that were involved in earlier eLTER projects, but also external scientists, including key figureheads/leading researchers who were specifically 'headhunted' to strengthen eLTER RIs whole systems approach, enrich the RI with top-tier specific expertise, and to open the RI to new research communities to participate in eLTER's scientific work. **The RC teams and the Case studies therein belong to the eLTER project components and are also visible in the eLTER environment mindmap (marked green), because they are fundamental for networking activities at the interface to the wider scientific communities.**

In eLTER PLUS, the researchers are gathered and coordinated by four distinguished Theme leads responsible for their RCs. The Theme leads represent their respective scientific communities, and are well recognized in both their own communities and within the eLTER community (Fig 7). They coordinate the theme-specific activities across all eLTER PLUS WPs and serve as key hubs for connecting to the various eLTER RI user communities. Importantly, each Theme lead is formally anchored in a coordinating task in the pivot WP10, responsible for interfacing between RC-specific service provisioning (e.g. pilot data products, virtual labs) and thematic user requirements. In this way, user requirements from both within and outside the eLTER RI can be accommodated through targeted service development.

Figure 7. The role of Theme leads in engaging the disciplinary communities as the foundation for the stakeholder engagement. Colour coding of the communities is reflecting the whole systems concept illustration in the bottom: pale blue: atmosphere, orange: social and economic sphere, green: biosphere, blue: hydrosphere, grey: geosphere. The figure will be elaborated further during the project lifetime.

The Theme leads and scientific communities are actively engaged in all project WPs, in addition to the WPs where they have specific scientific tasks. They contribute in developing scientific syntheses and advanced technical integration, thus shaping future RI development, including its long-term observation strategies and scientific research programmes. Theme leads play especially important roles in outlining the Strategic plan for eLTER RI, which is done in the PPP WP1.

In addition to their roles coordinating Theme activities within the eLTER RI initiatives, Theme leads are also responsible for serving as conduits for strengthening contacts with sister research infrastructures, research consortia, research centers, learned societies and academic departments and schools. Here, too, the objectives of the Theme leads are to both open up the RI for engagement of potential user communities and to encourage these stakeholders to utilize the RI resources, and to establish eLTER RI as a leading provider of research, monitoring data, and scientific knowledge. By facilitating this two-way interaction between eLTER RI and external scientific stakeholders, Theme leads contribute to enriching both the RI and the broader scientific community.

The concrete activities of the Theme leads comprised *inter alia*:

- In developing the first draft of the eLTER Standard Observations (eLTER PLUS WP3), the Theme leads and the scientific task leads and their peers in WP8 and WP9 played a central role. They developed a harmonized list of variables based on their specific data needs within the science cases and across their disciplinary objectives. Since the science cases relate to the basic eLTER research challenges this targeted list was a good start for further, iterative discussions with a broader groups of scientists within PLUS and PPP and outside (e.g., AQUACOSM, CLRTAP, SOIL BON) the projects.
- For Biodiversity Loss, a first set of standard observations was proposed in an iterative process. This process started with several (tele) conferences of a smaller group of BDL experts directly involved in the eLTER PLUS project. In a second step, all BDL experts from the entire eLTER community (incl.

PPP) have been consulted. Additionally, experts from other networks (e.g. AQUACOSM) have been approached and provided further input. An upcoming step will involve further high level biodiversity research outside eLTER.

- By participating horizontally across all eLTER PLUS WPs, the Theme leads continuously monitor and intervene in work group meetings to strengthen the Whole Systems approach. This is achieved, in part, by engaging WP leads and challenging them to broaden their disciplinary approaches to include interdisciplinary questions and research teams, consultation and integration of stakeholders (e.g., policy makers, farmers), or consulting with representatives of different theme groups to consider basic research questions or the broader implications of their research. The Theme leads also meet periodically among themselves to coordinate efforts and identify areas of concern for realizing our Whole Systems approach.
- Internal networking workshop were held during the spring 2021 consortium meeting ('Venus') to get to know and bring together experts in the different disciplinary fields of eLTER (particularly important for stakeholder screening was the collection of involvement of experts in the various scientific communities/RIs/monitoring networks)
- During the data gathering process for the several science cases, the Theme leads streamlined the exchange between Science Case leads (eLTER WP8 and WP9) and the data providers, i.e. SPCs. This way, we rendered a broader involvement of the entire scientific community within eLTER PLUS, which includes many SPCs, with the site and data providers.
- The Theme leads activated the eLTER scientific communities to multilateral communication. e.g. by hosting on-line theme meetings for all interested internal (eLTER PPP and PLUS) stakeholders (SE Theme meets two times annually) to discuss progress in eLTER PLUS, to review progress in standardizing and harmonizing SE data collection, to share research collaboration opportunities, and to discuss issues raised by members of the community.
- eLTER PLUS Theme 'Biogeochemical controls of ecosystem functions' strengthened the cooperation between eLTER and ICOS as a concrete pilot for co-location design and promoting the ideas during the eLTER Session at EGU 2021, April 19-30: <https://meetingorganizer.copernicus.org/EGU21/session/38832>. Whole system approach for in-situ & long-term environmental system research on life supporting systems (WAILS) Convener: Jaana Bäck, Co-conveners: Thomas Dirnböck, Ulf Mallast (ECS). The collaboration process is ongoing and will be followed up by the theme leads.
- Furthermore, the Theme leads promoted eLTER in several international publications, scientific conferences and research strategies (EU biodiversity partnership) as well as within the national research area. Some examples are:
 - Synthesis and review papers were published to increase eLTER visibility in hydrologic research and carbon cycle observation with proposing eLTER as key element in a terrestrial ecosystem reanalysis framework (Reanalysis in Earth System Science: Towards Terrestrial Ecosystem Reanalysis. Baatz et al 2020 <https://doi.org/10.1029/2020RG000715>)
 - Data combined from multiple eLTER sites matured a publication in Nature Communications: Meta-analysis of multidecadal biodiversity trends in Europe: Pilotto et al. 2020 <https://www.nature.com/articles/s41467-020-17171-y>
 - High visibility of eLTER at international conferences was assured through e.g. highlight talks at EGU (European Geoscience Union General Assembly) 2021, April 19-30: <https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-egu21-9426> and during the OZCAR TERENO network co-organization of International Conference in Strasbourg, France on Oct. 5 - Oct. 7 2021
 - eLTER site PIs drive the identification of hydrologic key observations from hydrologic research perspective by co-initiation of "A European vision for hydrological observations and experimentation" Galileo Conference on 19–22 September 2022, Naples, Italy
 - Analysis of co-located eLTER, ICOS and Fluxnet sites explores the impact of extreme events on ecosystem dynamics and the water-food-climate nexus. The data feeds into a pan-European land surface modeling framework which will serve as basis to terrestrial ecosystem reanalysis products.

- Socio-Ecology Theme lead presentation at the 2021 annual meeting of the International Association of Landscape Ecology. Presentation entitled, “What’s Possible for Integrating European Social-Ecological Research?”
 - Socio-Ecology Theme lead preparing manuscript for special issue of “Landscape Ecology” entitled, “Operationalizing Transdisciplinary Research in Europe: The Evolution of the Long-Term Social Ecological Research (LTSER) Platform”
 - Socio-Ecology Theme lead participated and presented in symposium organized by the Canadian NSERC ResNet on the subject of “Lessons Learned from the Startup Phase of Environmental Research Networks” (participants included representatives from seven environmental research and monitoring networks, and they are currently working on a joint manuscript tentatively entitled “Inventing and reinventing environmental knowledge networks: 10 questions to (re)invigorate collaboration”).
- The BGC Theme lead Thomas Dirnböck further negotiated the cooperation letter between eLTER and the various monitoring networks under the UNECE Working Group of Effects (WGE). Final version is still under development (see also Table 1).
 - The BDL Theme lead Peter Haase established a cooperation with SOIL BON to jointly investigate soil biodiversity using eLTER sites and to establish the Nagoya protocol allowing for centralized analyses of DNA (metabarcoding).
 - The SES Theme lead Daniel Orenstein presented for the NATURA network, focusing on urban LTSER research and emphasizing opportunities for NATURA members to utilize the eLTER RI.

The most recent activity to engage the scientific communities is the creation of several Expert Groups (EGs), including high level experts from the project and from external, related networks and communities. The EGs have been nominated for consultations in core processes, eg. the eLTER Standard Observations scheme and Definitions of site categories (eLTER PLUS WP3, eLTER PPP WP6) (see Annex 2 and 3). The work of the EGs is just starting.

3.2 Peers in environmental research and observation

The third stakeholder group is the currently most important one due to the relevance for the eLTER design and detailed specification of eLTER RI’s role as a member of the European ESFRI Landscape. This relevance is also clearly reflected by the high number of peers, with which eLTER experts involve and are related to the existing pool of in-situ facilities (see left branches of the eLTER environment mind map).

The peer Research Infrastructures and networks in environmental research in Europe form a cluster that has been closely collaborating for over a decade, and funded by the European Commission FP7 and H2020 Framework Programmes in projects ENVRI, ENVRIplus and ENVRI FAIR. The ENVRI projects have aimed at improving the Earth observation monitoring systems and strategies, including actions to improve harmonization and innovation, and generating common solutions to many shared information technology and data related challenges. They also sought to harmonize policies for access and provide strategies for knowledge transfer amongst RIs. The consortium partners shared a common motivation derived from the global grand challenges (climate change, food security, environmental risks, sustainable use of natural resources, etc.) and from the UN SDGs, which each of the partners address with their specific methods and tools. The different terrestrial RIs clustered within ENVRI have a high potential of scientific cooperation, co-location and data interoperability.

The eLTER RI is embedded in the Biosphere and Ecosystems domain of ESFRI, as described e.g. in ENVRIplus landscape analysis, visualised in Figure 8. This illustration clearly shows that the user needs and the services provided to society by the environmental infrastructures in different domains are very much interlinked and no one RI will be able to solve the Grand Challenges alone. The landscape analysis also reveals how RIs within a domain are able to complement each other and jointly provide tools and solutions for societies to tackle the challenges. It is conceivable that the cooperating environmental RIs constitute a federated landscape, acting together as a cooperative very large-scale pan-European facility. In addition to this, we

can identify several bilateral interactions of the research infrastructures in the Biosphere domain that will help to optimise complementary services and synergies for integrated research projects.

Figure 8: The ENVRiplus concept of environmental research infrastructure domains and their interdependencies. Figure: Asmi et al (2014)

Being part of the ENVRi community has formed a good foundation for bi- and multilateral collaboration in key activities. The potential for harmonization and coordination of activities among the RIs, such as development of core variables, data interoperability, strategic co-location and efficient cross-RI cooperation were outlined in Kutsch et al. (2017).

Basically, a comprehensive cross-infrastructure documentation describing multiple use of sites is still missing. eLTER has initiated a harmonized documentation of all in situ observational sites and facilities in a common database, DEIMS SDR. Currently, several RIs and networks have already been described by a few fundamental DEIMS attributes, resulting in a broad availability of site metadata from a large number of co-located sites. DEIMS can be used e.g., in searching the best possible combination of sites for addressing a specific research question.

The co-location (several RIs and networks operating at the same location) is a way to search for a higher impact and to avoid duplication of efforts, and eLTER is determined to test and screen the opportunities for this. Shared administration, harmonized observational schemes and joint facilities and staff are increasing cost-efficiency and adding scientific value to the research done at the co-located sites.

The environmental RI landscape has developed in many phases during several ESFRI Roadmap periods since the first Roadmap in 2006. It is clear that all environmental RIs have to work out their own specific profiles and competences, and in doing so, also actively search for collaboration and complementarities (see Fig 9A, B). eLTER has actively pursued discussions and developed concepts for better integration of the components in the environmental RI domain. The bilateral consultations have led to designing of Letters of Support or Memoranda of Understanding between eLTER and other RIs and networks (Table 1).

Table 1. eLTER-initiated actions towards coordination and collaboration between RIs and networks. MoU = Memorandum of Understanding, MoC=Memorandum of Collaboration, LoS= Letter of Support

RI/network	key action towards collaboration agreement/implementation	status
ICOS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Collaboration letter • co-location opportunities explored • joint scientific sessions 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • approved by ICOS GA, 2021 • vEGU20221
AnaEE	dialogue about collaboration	initiated, joint proposals developed for HE
LifeWatch	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • MoU • experts meeting on IT planned 	2017 MoU existing, 2021 update in preparation
Danubius	MoU position paper and suggested activities at pilot sites	in preparation in preparation
ICP Forests	MoU	in preparation
Aquacosc	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Support letter • Joint concept paper 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • provided in 2018 • in preparation
UNECE Working Group of Effects (WGE)	MoC	final negotiations
Mountain Research Initiative	Participation as Associate Partner in Preparatory Phase through ETH Zürich	in preparation
DiSSCo	eLTER participated in Infrastructure Contact Zones analysis Trilateral MoC with GBIF envisaged	in preparation
Jerico	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • LoS • Joint concept paper 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ready (2020) • in preparation
Interact	harmonization of site attributes in DEIMS SDR	ready
Programme on Ecosystem Change and Society	Presentation of eLTER RI to PECS board in 2020	Initial dialogue done
MAB - Man and the Environment Biosphere Initiative	Initial contact made; discussion to share spatial data to assess site overlap (in context of ILTER)	Initial dialogue done
NATURA network	Presentation of eLTER made to network; ongoing discussion of collaboration potential	Ongoing discussion

Figure 9. (A) The complementary roles as well as the services the environmental RIs provide to diverse user communities. The central part represents the complementary and interoperable in situ networks for standardised large scale observations (ICOS, ACTRIS), natural and socio-ecological systems research (LTER, SIOS) and experimentation (AnaEE, AQUACOSM). These in situ infrastructures provide data for the infrastructures above, dealing with modelling, data analysis and workflow automation (e.g. LifeWatch) and supporting system understanding, predictions and decision-making. Modelling and analyses feed their parameter requirements back to the data generating units. All RIs should make use of generic supporting e-infrastructures and reference infrastructures such as EUDAT, EOSC and DiSSCo (in the bottom). Scientific and other user communities (at the top) will benefit from the cooperating RIs. Figure 4 (B) reveals the detailed operational links and interactions between eLTER and sister-RIs and projects. The relations with in situ RIs (n green, ICOS, ACTRIS, SIOS, AQUACOSM, AnaEE) emerge from co-location and harmonisation of parameters and methods, whereas collaboration with the generic and e-infrastructures is important in developing e.g. semantics and data flows, management, and storage (DiSSCo, LifeWatch, EUDAT). DiSSCo and AQUACOSM are not yet established as legal entities, AnaEE will be an ERIC in the beginning of 2022.

In the broader European environmental research network landscape where, over decades, numerous projects, flagships and initiatives have been established, eLTER is working in close interaction, developing many types of common interfaces and services (Figure 10). The contributions and co-developing of services between eLTER and the other initiatives are realised in e.g. semantics, metadata and site description, data flows, standards and harmonisation, and user group involvement.

Figure 10: An overview of the relationship between eLTER and the different user and service provider groups in the environmental research field. TOP: eLTER RI as contributing, Bottom: eLTER RI as receiving party in collaboration. The groups are not fully exhaustive and the figure represents the status as of 2016, but shows some of the exemplary operational links between the initiatives from eLTER perspective.

Of importance in the practical implementation of the RI-RI relationship is the unequal distribution of national memberships in the environmental RIs, reflected in the national RI roadmaps. Many European countries have prioritized the roadmap RIs in the national funding schemes, but very few recognize the concrete steps towards an integration between RIs. eLTER aims at actively pursuing the inclusion of the national LTER networks and eLTER RI in all national roadmaps, and in this way opening the possibilities for

receiving national support to the eLTER Sites and Platforms. This has been done through the support to National Coordinators by providing them with a rich source of background materials, sharing examples from other countries' successful processes, and convening them in regular meetings for exchange and updates, helping in their roadmap and funding application writing, and even personal visits to support their national processes.

Globally, eLTER RI is leadingly involved in the International LTER Network ILTER, as well as in the Global Ecosystem Research Infrastructure GERI.

ILTER (International Long Term Ecological Research Network) is a network of networks, encompassing ca. 800 LTER research sites and ca. 70 LTER platforms, located in a wide array of ecosystems that can help understand environmental change across the globe. ILTER's focus is on long-term, site-based research and monitoring in a globally distributed network in the fields of ecosystem, biodiversity, critical zone and socio-ecological research. ILTER is a legal entity since 2007, and supported by membership fees by participating networks.

The LTER Europe network provides a majority of LTER sites and platforms globally (almost 60%). eLTER has been among the key contributors in ILTER, driving the development of ILTER to secure highest quality interoperable services in close interaction with the participating regional and global research infrastructures and networks. Majority of sites and platforms listed in ILTER (in DEIMS SDR) are located in Europe, and the concept of 'Whole System Approach' was initiated from the vision of the LTER Europe network.

GERI (Global Ecosystem Research Infrastructure) is comprised of the site-based research infrastructures of its founding members, which are CERN, eLTER, ICOS, NEON, SAEON and TERN. The GERI was initiated in several workshops (Zhaoging, Boulder, Washington DC) among the founding members, where the development and governance processes, operational status and overarching goals of each GERI member were discussed. In these workshops, an overarching agreement was reached of the necessity to aim at complementary and harmonized observations in all continents. The Group of Senior Officials (GSO) on global Research Infrastructures recognized GERI as an important initiative for establishing a distributed ecosystem Research infrastructure, being able to respond to the global grand challenges.

The vision of GERI is to provide and advocate a vision for a global Research Infrastructure providing terrestrial and coastal in-situ observations from a high number of observational sites, organized in a common hierarchical system and standardized in the highest possible degree. GERI is dedicated to providing interoperable FAIR data that delivers a better understanding of the function and change of indicator ecosystems from terrestrial, freshwater and coastal environments across global biomes to support excellent science that can inform political and managerial decision-making addressing grand societal challenges. As a peer group, GERI is able to support the more efficient and structured development of eLTER RI.

This effort reflects the current transition across many countries of observational networks and projects towards stable research infrastructures. The GERI founders advocate cooperation and common activities among Research Infrastructures that have already achieved a high internal organization and legal structure, but also exchange of experience with, and support for networks that have only recently initiated this process. GERI has been established under a Memorandum of Understanding (Annex 4) signed in 2019–2020 by its founding members. GERI governance is being developed by working groups, along with guidelines to allow additional members to be recognised within the GERI framework.

3.3 Linkages to shareholders involved in the Interim Council decision making

For the formal engagement of countries committed to support the development of eLTER RI, eLTER PPP has designed the Interim Council (IC), a body with decision-making power over the legal, governance and financial decisions needed for the implementation of planned RI. eLTER PPP supports the work of IC and its

chair to establish the eLTER legal entity. eLTER IC meets approximately twice a year. 18 countries are formally involved in the eLTER IC through their national delegations nominated by the relevant ministries responsible for ESFRI activities. The eLTER IC is the highest decision-making body for the eLTER RI strategic development, funding decisions, and country involvement in the eLTER ERIC (European Research Infrastructure Consortium, Council Regulation (EC) No 723/2009). The eLTER IC discusses and approves legal, governance and financial matters, eLTER Site and eLTER Platform labelling and location of Central Services on the way towards implementation of the eLTER RI. Thus, the role of the IC is to make decisions for implementing eLTER RI. The eLTER IC decided in December 2020 to strive for an ERIC structure to coordinate and lead the activities of the eLTER RI.

The role of eLTER PLUS in connection with the IC is to collect and prioritize user needs and to pilot and test priority components. Strictly requirements based services, consolidated with the users, will ensure a cost-efficient and highly relevant RI. While eLTER PPP aims to formalise operations, eLTER PLUS strives to engage the best expertise and infrastructure available for integrated research on European ecosystems, and to optimize and advance the collaborative use of these services by key user groups. Through PPP the results of PLUS are concretely taken as ingredients in the eLTER ESFRI process towards an operational research infrastructure, and presented to the Interim Council for their decisions. PLUS activities linked to IC decisions comprise the piloting of data discovery, visualization and analytical tools, collating suggestions for standard observations, agreeing a feasible site design, identifying the most suited sites and data sources for piloting workflows and processes, ensuring the scientific relevance, creating partnerships and collaborations with research communities, and continuous monitoring and collecting user feedback concerning the pilot services. PLUS not only facilitates the creation of innovative pilot tools, but also their uptake at the sites and platforms (linkage with the SPCs and SPF related activities above) and disseminates the scientific results to relevant audiences.

4 Priority actions within eLTER PLUS with stakeholder groups

To intensify the general and stakeholder-specific engagement, eLTER PLUS will continue addressing the following priority items:

1. **General approach for continuous interactions and information exchange - Engaging with the stakeholder groups through Key accounts (persons to create and develop the contacts with the stakeholders):** The linkages and connections between the 'eLTER Key accounts' and the detailed stakeholder groups were discussed in a WP2 meeting dedicated to the mind mapping. The next steps are to decide on some key accounts (in case of several candidates), define priority actions at each interface, and create a roadmap for the process of systematically screening for priority interaction point like key events, targeted sessions therein or joint training activities. The results of this screening will be passed to the related eLTER PLUS and eLTER PPP Work packages (WP6 for communication, WP5 for training). Further, a tracking mechanism for quantitatively documenting major interactions and outcomes by the respective key accounts will be established.
2. **The LTER National Coordinators and SPCs:** The SPCs will be the main target group for the eLTER PLUS activities, while the more formal interactions with NCs are leadingly organized by the eLTER PPP. In the future the SPF meetings will be continued biannually and a new format (webinar series at an interval of 2-3 months) is under discussion. In addition, the SPCs will be encouraged to participate in events organized by the eLTER projects. The 4 SPF working groups will be monitored closely for progress and supported where needed from the eLTER PLUS project. A broadened participation from all participating countries and categories of SPCs is anticipated in the coming year with directed information campaigns via national coordinators, peer-to-peer networks and invitations to broadly engaging activities related to e.g. training and data strategies. The NCs are invited to all meetings as well to be informed about the ongoing activities. They are also informed in a targeted way in regular NC meetings convened by eLTER PPP.

3. **Researchers and science stakeholders:** With the leadership of the Theme leads, the researchers will be commenting and further streamlining the eLTER Standard observations in a concerted manner with their scientific peers in eLTER PLUS. They will also support the discretization of the site and network design, defining and developing pilot data workflows together with WP10 and WP 11 of eLTER PLUS, and further strengthen the scientific cooperation between WP8 and WP9 science cases and SPCs. The Theme leads will continue to promote eLTER through scientific outputs. Expanding discussions on eLTER Standard observation beyond eLTER by consulting external researchers and scientific stakeholders takes place in the dedicated Expert Groups.
4. **Peers in environmental research and observation RIs:** eLTER is a key player in the global development, contributing to GSO and ESFRI (co-location, integration). In close interaction with eLTER PPP, the eLTER PLUS WP2 will (in a two-stage procedure) mainly explore the willingness to co-operate and outline areas of potential collaboration. The eLTER environment mindmap serves as quantitative basis for this screening. In a second step, the relevance of these collaborations for the eLTER RI design, service development and formalization will be analyzed together with the team of eLTER PPP WP1 on strategies. For now, the agreed priorities of eLTER PLUS networking activities are ICOS, DANUBIUS, AnaEE, UNECE ICPs, LifeWatch, ENVRI, ILTER, GERI, NEON, SAEON and TERN.

5 Conclusions

Overall, the main challenge for the networking by eLTER PLUS WP2 is the high diversity of relevant elements in eLTER's environment, which is closely linked to the thematic breadth intrinsically caused by the Whole System Approach as core element of the eLTER Science Case. eLTER depends on a wide range of disciplines collaborating at its facilities and using its services in doing so. This bears the risk of conflicts with other projects, communities and networks, specifically if the added value of collaboration is overlooked and eLTER rather perceived as a successful competitor. However, we have been receiving very positive feedback about our inclusiveness and openness, which will help to overcome this obstacle. The eLTER PLUS networking activities have already prompted several concrete results with peers thematically closest to eLTER and most relevant for its design, namely ICOS and the UNECE WGE International Cooperative Programmes.

The importance of internal stakeholders is becoming more and more evident when the concrete suggestions of the organization and services of the RI are emerging. Thus, the activities will be intensifying during the project lifetime, with the help of the SPF concept and the national coordinators' engagement. It is very promising that the SPCs are actively participating in updating their site information in DEIMS SDR, in working groups of the SPF, and in outreach activities of their site specific activities.

A challenge is the need to focus activities, where the close interaction with eLTER PPP and the eLTER ESFRI process gives good guidance. This also means that the responsibilities of stakeholder relationships have to be distributed to the key accounts. From all analyses it became evident that a strong emphasis has to be put on up to now less covered stakeholder categories in the eLTER environment like the civil society organizations and business & industry, where related eLTER PLUS tasks will start soon.

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ANNEX 1 SPF concept paper

v08, 2020-11-29

The eLTER Sites and Platforms Forum (SPF)

Concept note elaborated by the eLTER PLUS WP2.2 team and the National LTER Coordinators

Most important acronyms (for detailed definitions see dedicated section of the document):

NC – National Coordinator: national LTER network and ESFRI process coordinator, representative of a country in LTER Europe

SPC – Site and Platform Coordinators

SPF – Site and Platforms Forum

1. Introduction

The eLTER Sites and LTER Platforms distributed across Europe make up the backbone of the foreseen eLTER Research Infrastructure (RI). Historically, the European LTER process has been promoted and governed by bottom-up initiatives, where the focus has been on establishing and coordinating national networks. In spite of their crucial roles in this process, the LTER Site and Platform Coordinators (SPCs) have not had a specific forum or platform for communication and exchange or for establishing joint activities (e.g. training), at least not as a peer group across countries. The recent inclusion of eLTER in the ESFRI Roadmap (European Strategy Forum for Research Infrastructures) provides a historical chance for implementing centralized and top-down components of eLTER with organizational support by the Preparatory Phase Project ([eLTER PPP](#)). This urgently calls for efficient information exchange with the SPCs. Besides the general need for better networking, the **Sites and Platforms do have the opportunity to design and co-create their future working environment at the national and European scales, - including the services and tools eLTER should provide.**

Besides from the critically important role as the eLTER National Research Infrastructure components (NRIs), the SPCs' prioritized requirements, experiences and expertise are key in the "eLTER ESFRI process".

To support such an inclusive process, the networking Work Package of [eLTER PLUS Advanced Community](#) project has collaborated with the national LTER coordinators to initiate a **Site and Platforms Forum**, the **SPF**.

What will the SPF bring to the SPCs:

- a forum and platform for peer networking
- new perspectives and visions for sustainable operations of Sites and Platforms
- sharing of experiences, expertise and success stories
- a strong voice in developing the eLTER (nationally, internationally) and mandate for initiating joint activities and thereby shape the emerging infrastructure
- inputs on desired specifications and prioritization services including e.g., IT-resources and support
- joint planning of activities that are more efficiently organized in a collective manner or through central services than at the site or country level
- increased visibility and profiles of Sites and Platforms
- clarifying and broadly promoting the professional identity and competences of SPCs

2. Who are invited to SPF

The significance and mandate of the Site and Platform Coordinators (SPCs) is well recognized, even considering the many synonyms we historically have been using: Primary investigators (PIs), site managers, site coordinators, LTSER Platform managers, etc. The diversity of synonyms indicate that SPCs have roles beyond management and infrastructure leadership, specifically reaching into the science domain, and also highlight that their job profiles and terms are not necessarily very well defined. The roles may also vary across countries and institutions. In the eLTER process, the persons having following tasks or roles are welcome to participate in the SPF:

- persons taking responsibility for sites and platforms
- persons having the best overview of a local site or a platform
- persons seen as the right one to “speak for or represent the site or the platform”
- other key persons that keep sites or platforms up and running and contribute to their development, in all or several of the following indicative ways:
 - lobbying and profiling, internal/external fundraising
 - scientific leadership
 - connecting disciplinary work and teams
 - coordination of site/platform data and metadata
 - experts in charge for site specific contributions in synthesis papers
 - those in charge of administration and organization related to the site
 - those deciding on observational design, instrumentation or other forms of development at the sites
 - individuals mandated to handle questions of site involvements in European scale RIs

The seemingly wide variety of roles and functions of SPCs imply involvement in numerous situations, networks, and expert groups relevant for eLTER. SPCs do not necessarily need to have a formalized job description designed to deal with this broad combination of responsibilities while this more clearly is the case for some nationally coordinated infrastructures.

3. What is the purpose of SPF?

The SPF will have two parallel goals:

- Specify what framework and services the SPCs need
- Plan how the SPF can contribute to meeting these needs

The European eLTER process aims to implement an operative research infrastructure with both centralised and distributed components, primarily to enable top-level science. For this reason, it is very important that the SPC are aware that the Sites and Platforms they are coordinating are a core operational part of the future eLTER RI. Equally importantly, the SPCs also represent the main internal user group benefiting from Central Services. Thus, during the eLTER preparation phase the SPCs are invited to clearly specify and prioritize support services needed by the Sites and Platforms.

Examples of topics the SPF will address:

- identify relevant technology developments and emerging tools to ensure continued technical state of the art,
- identify and co-organise training on e.g. eLTER Standard Observation variables (essential ecosystem variables), new methods and workflows, site management, visualisation, data analysis, stakeholder engagement, whole system approach, and outreach
- create certificates through training and professional performance in order to elevate the career appreciation and task descriptions of staff engaged in running eLTER sites

- address and point out emerging scientific questions relevant for the RI operations or harmonisation and design of protocols
- promote site activities and celebrate the ‘eLTER champions’ (exemplary solutions, findings and successes)
- coordinate co-authorships of e.g. data papers
- facilitate the launch of new projects and stimulate joint funding initiatives and cross-site projects
- facilitate and promote joint procurements and shared instrumentation
- collect promising ideas for broad eLTER implementation, innovative actions and links to SMEs
- investigate experiences and best practices in collaboration with peer RIs in Europe and globally.

These topics and the means needed to make progress will be further discussed and elaborated as the SPF convenes. A first brainstorming on topics such as data, observations, stakeholders, management and careers can be found in the annex.

4. Organisation and activities

The SPF is challenged to find the best possible way of actively interacting with the National Coordinators (NC), the eLTER ESFRI process coordination and ongoing eLTER projects (currently eLTER PPP and eLTER PLUS), which can support these activities. There are first ideas developed by the SPCs networking team of eLTER PLUS, led by Stefan Bertilsson, and by the National Coordinators. These ideas shall be presented and discussed at the first SPF meeting.

The SPF is envisaged to be a platform for networking and coordination of the SPCs peer group (“a strong community of highly interactive and scientifically coherent but geographically dispersed teams”). Still, communication and interactions over the past months have given evidence that the SPCs are not a homogeneous group. Strengths, interests and needs differ according to the situation of the sites (organisation, funding etc.), the composition of the site teams. The organisation, overall scope and range of activities of the SPF will strongly depend on the identified clusters of interests and requirements. The SPF may ad hoc appoint sub-groups (e.g. habitat specific or other topical or geographically -related working groups) and contribute to bodies and structures of the eLTER process to secure proper consideration of interests and experiences from the SPCs peer group. Working groups could e.g. be asked to provide solicited inputs on infrastructure design and instrumentation from an SPCs perspective or prioritize future activities and capacity building within the eLTER RI.

Irrespective of these first thoughts and without anticipating any detail we envisage that the SPF will have regular meetings:

- physical meetings (general and targeted)
- virtual meetings (general and targeted to specific groups/topics)
- webinars

If considered useful and desirable, the work of the SPF could be centrally supported with virtual tools to maintain and increase synergies, coordination and collaboration, for example:

- virtual platform for FAQs, chat and anonymous feedback on process and events
- open forum for bottom-up initiatives, calls for collaboration and assistance
- access to information about tools and data to visualize and analyse the eLTER RI development
- production of promotional and educational materials such as instructional videos, an updated site catalog, “who’s who in eLTER” and a labelling process for identification of high-quality eLTER sites.
- a dedicated webpage under the eLTER website umbrella.

The meetings of the SPF could be organised back to back with concurrent eLTER project meetings or organised so that participating institutions would take turns in hosting the events. The meetings should have a chair and an agenda. Both currently running projects and the central eLTER coordination office could support the chairs in their work.

Annex to SPF concept paper

First brainstorming on potential issues in the future SPF agenda (eLTER PLUS, WP2 team)

Data

One of the key issues is data interoperability and management. This includes common practices, principles for sharing, process, and tools. The SPF could discuss and provide input on how to enhance usage of DEIMS with regards to the design and user interface, but also with regards to developing cross-site data products, that may involve standard protocols for data curation and validation of data quality, conversion to common standards and data transfer services. This would also entail inputs and feedback on standardized vocabulary and metadata structure proposed top-down.

Observations

Observations present their own unique challenges. These include e.g. harmonisation and quality management for observations, Essential Ecosystem Variables, piloting new methods, brokering cutting-edge research, filling gaps in observations and methods, ground-truthing and testbeds for big data, cost-efficient observational methods, and partnerships with private sector and innovation organizations for use of new sensor & observation technology. The SPCs are in a unique position to provide advice on valuable advances, rational implementation, priorities and could act as contact points for SMEs and other stakeholders.

Stakeholders

The SPCs are firmly anchored in the stations and in this capacity are suitable brokers for exchanging experiences and knowledge about how to effectively engage local and regional stakeholders and e.g., explore the possibilities to expand classical LTER sites to eLTER platforms. SPF can discuss and increase the awareness of the societal impact of the sites and platforms, and how we could monitor and report on that to the funding agencies and hosting institutions. Other valuable inputs could be strategies for citizen science projects and improvement of socio-ecological science tools.

Management

The SPF could substantially increase the efficiency of site management, thereby saving resources. This could be done by sharing and creating best practices and document and share valuable lessons learned in practical work of site management and operations, e.g. how to deal with the co-localization issues, budget cuts and what makes a site successful. The SPCs also has a valuable role in locally promoting eLTER initiatives and opportunities for research.

Careers

The SPF could contribute to the currently highlighted topic of careers and career development for individuals working at the interface of technical site and platform operations, research and management. For such research infrastructure professionals, there is typically no clear job profile or career path, and as a result many SPCs are not well acknowledged or recognized, neither within their institutions, nor beyond within the scientific community at large. The SPF could enable training certificates, propose and promote the broader use of job profiles with widely acknowledged descriptions that should ideally be interoperable with other distributed environmental research infrastructures (RIs). This development would over time be highly beneficial, particularly for young researchers looking for positions and careers rather within the RI operation than in more widely recognized academic career tracks. In eLTER, it is possible to advance and promote their careers and enhance the appreciation of site and platform managers to a higher level.

ANNEX 2. eLTER Expert Group (EG) GUIDELINES

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M. Mirtl, J. Bäck, S. Zacharias, N. Nikolaidis

Preamble

In order to implement the whole system approach, a wide range of disciplines need to collaborate at eLTER Sites and eLTER Platforms in truly multidisciplinary integrated research (earth, soil and critical zone science, hydrological and hydrometeorological science, ecosystem and socio-ecological science). Each of the scientific communities need to be serviced according to their fundamental disciplinary requirements. This comprises standard observations carried out by the distributed sites in appropriate observational/experimental designs and the provisioning of relevant data from other sources as part of eLTER Research Infrastructure (RI) central services. Moreover, the prioritization of data needs should consider their relevance beyond individual disciplines, e.g., the usage of variables in modelling and their role as change indicators across ecosystem compartments.

Cross-disciplinarity is crucial for „Whole System“ research on the life supporting system

The eLTER ESFRI process capitalizes on two major EC H2020 projects designed to interact closely. eLTER PLUS tests existing RI components and further conceptualizes eLTER RI alongside scientific case studies covering the eLTER “Themes” (Research Challenges of eLTER: biodiversity, biogeochemical controls of ecosystem functions, climate water-food nexus, socio-ecological systems). eLTER PLUS also prioritizes future RI services and implements service pilots, e.g., supporting scientific data and analytical workflows. eLTER PPP feeds the identified priorities into the eLTER RI formalization process facilitating decision making of the funding shareholders across 20 countries and the establishment of the legal entity.

The task teams of the eLTER PPP and eLTER PLUS are in charge of (1) producing the documents and discussion papers needed for decision making about the design, costs and governance of the eLTER RI, and (2) managing multi-stage consultation processes towards these documents. These Guidelines outline the purpose and role of the **Expert Groups (EG) in the context of this consultation process**.

Purpose and role

In addition to the disciplinary breadth of eLTER PLUS and the sound anchoring of the Thematic teams (Research Challenges) in their respective peer communities, the eLTER ESFRI process strives for maximizing eLTER RI’s relevance. This vision closely relates to the **purposes** for creating EGs:

- (1) through consulting with experts and communities beyond the actual project consortia limits
- (2) securing that eLTER RI seamlessly fits into the European and global landscape of environmental Research Infrastructures and observation networks, and

- (3) serve multiple communities, accommodating their networking efforts and identity.

To this end, the EG shall be established, which mirror major components of eLTER RIs environment and user groups collaborating at eLTER Sites and eLTSE Platforms or in using their comprehensive information clusters.

The major **roles** of the EGs are:

- critical review of discussion and concept papers on the eLTER design
- bringing viewpoints of the respective potential user group of future eLTER RI services (securing buy-in and service take-up)
- raise awareness amongst user groups and collaborators of
 - the starting specification process and the window of opportunity to co-design eLTER RI
 - the potential for coordinated joint activities, including co-location and co-design of services with other RIs and networks

In the current phase 2021/2022 of the eLTER ESFRI process, the eLTER RI design and service components of highest relevance are:

- the eLTER Standard Observations framework
- the eLTER Site and eLTSE Platform design (site categories)
- the eLTER Service Portfolio

Members, nomination and establishment

The EGs are platforms for an in-depth dialogue between eLTER consortium experts in the topical area and the external experts. This composition shall guarantee the provisioning of contextual information about concepts elaborated by the eLTER consortium to the external experts. Open questions by the external experts should be clarified ad hoc to pave the way for targeted discussions of remaining critical points.

The process of nomination and establishment of an EG comprises the following steps:

1. Nomination of convener and co-convener
 - by eLTER Coordination
 - convener is an expert, but should not have a leading role in the eLTER projects WPs in the given field
 - convener and co-convener are nominated accounting for the gender balance aspects as much as possible
2. Nomination of members
 - Indicative maximum size of an EG is 15 members
 - Conveners and eLTER Coordination elaborate a list of candidates
 - Consultation with SCs, NCs and SAB
 - The conveners will be involved in the final decision making by the Coordination
 - The EG can start activities before the maximum number of participants is reached and new experts can be nominated according to the needs and possibilities to contribute (e.g. experts from the countries)
3. Modus Operandi
 - PPP WP2 prepares the Rules of Procedure
 - An EG works within its mandate and reports to the respective PPP WP (--> SCs and Coordination)
 - The conveners will act as rapporteurs of the EG's suggestions.
4. Processing of input
 - The further processing of EG input is specified in the respective processes in the given matters (timing and decision making)
 - All these processes will serve the ultimate goal of presenting the design and services for the eLTER RI to be decided in the Interim Council

ANNEX 3 eLTER Expert Group (EG) Rules of Procedure

Purpose and composition

The purpose, tasks and the structure of the Expert Groups (EGs) are described in the EGs' Guidelines, as well as the process for initial establishment of the EG.

Membership

Membership in the EG is described in the EGs' Guidelines.

New experts can be nominated according to the needs based on the process described in the EGs' Guidelines.

Chair

Each EG elects a Chair from amongst the members. The Chair keeps the office until further decision by the EG.

Meetings and meeting preparation

The meetings are convened upon request of the Chair. The meetings and the material under discussion should be announced early enough to allow members of the EGs to prepare. Meetings can be organised virtually or face-to-face.

The coordinators of the PPP and PLUS projects, and the eLTER PPP WP 6 lead are allowed to participate in the EG meetings as observers. The Chair of an EG can invite other participants when necessary, such as the eLTER projects' WP, task or theme leads, or other contributors.

The EGs will receive material and background documents from eLTER PPP WPs (e.g., WP5 and WP6). Material and documents to be discussed in the EG meetings are prepared by the teams of the eLTER PPP and eLTER PLUS. eLTER PPP WP6 is in charge of submitting and coordinating the relevant material and requests to the Chair of the relevant EG.

The conveners and co-conveners shall have a joint plenary at least once a year.

Meeting agenda and minutes

The Chair makes sure that each meeting has an agenda, and prepares it together with the Convener (see Guidelines). The Chair makes sure that the minutes are written that indicate what was discussed, and what the end result was. Minutes shall be archived in the eLTER repository.

Working mode at the meetings

The EGs are platforms for an in-depth dialogue between eLTER consortium experts in the topical area and the external experts. Therefore the EGs shall always aim for consensus decisions and recommendations. There is no quorum requirement for the meetings to reach end results that are recorded in the minutes.

Reporting

The EGs works according to the task description given in EGs' Guidelines and reports through the mechanism provided for each of the matters like the Standard Observations consultation process. The reporting will be explained in dedicated teleconferences.

ANNEX 4. Memorandum of Understanding of the Global Ecosystem Research Infrastructure GERI

MEMORANDUM OF UNDERSTANDING

Between the:

**Chinese Ecosystem Research Network (CERN), China,
European Long-Term Ecosystem Research – Research Infrastructure (eLTER RI), Europe,
Integrated Carbon Observation System – European Research Infrastructure Consortium (ICOS
ERIC), Europe,
National Ecological Observatory Network (NEON), USA,
the South African Environmental Observation Network (SAEON), South Africa,
Terrestrial Ecosystem Research Network (TERN), Australia.**

hereinafter referred to individually as ‘a Party’ or collectively as ‘the Parties’.

PREAMBLE

WHEREAS the Parties:

AGREE to address urgent global environmental challenges such as climate change, loss of biological diversity and invasive species, eutrophication of soils and surface waters, and changes in atmospheric chemistry;

AFFIRMINE that research on and continuous, long-term observations of terrestrial ecosystems are required to support knowledge-based societal action on these urgent environmental challenges;

EMPHASIZE that the knowledge base for a better understanding of ecosystem functions across biomes requires a balanced approach of observational and research infrastructure, data and modelling capacities, scientific evaluation and technical innovation;

ACKNOWLEDGE that the transition from networks to research infrastructures and with that standardized, stable and sustained measurements is an important step to advance terrestrial and coastal ecosystem research, and a global cooperation of research infrastructures is an essential step forward;

CONSIDER that observing essential variables are required to support the work of the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC), the United Nations Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD), the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC), and the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services (IPBES);

RECOGNIZE that UNFCCC and CBD call on their own parties to promote and cooperate in the systematic observation at global scale through the Global Climate Observing System (GCOS) and the Biodiversity Observation Networks (BONs);

ACKNOWLEDGE foundational efforts to encourage and to support global cooperation by the International Long-Term Ecological Research network (ILTER) and the Group on Earth Observations (GEO), and aiming to actively use ILTER and GEO as ongoing frameworks to support global cooperation;

The Parties have agreed on the following Memorandum of Understanding hereinafter referred to as ‘MoU’:

Article 1. Background

The transition from observational terrestrial networks to research infrastructures has been conducted on all continents over the past decade, and has come about because of new approaches to generate knowledge and to advance our ecological understanding. This also creates the unique opportunity (and obvious necessity) to further advance cooperation among these research infrastructures in order to address global environmental challenges and generate new opportunities to advance science. The Parties now face the programmatic challenge to find the appropriate development path to define the consequent organizational framework and to develop the respective procedural rules for this process.

The Parties agree to actively address these tasks while also acknowledging the integrative work conducted and still ongoing by the different participants.

Article 2. Purpose

The overarching goal of this MoU is to provide and advocate a vision for a global Research Infrastructure making terrestrial and coastal *in-situ* observations. This MoU describes the joint relationship among the Parties and what they wish to achieve. The Parties agree that such global Research Infrastructure shall include a high number of observational sites, organized in a common hierarchical system and standardized in the highest possible degree. This effort reflects the current transition of many observational networks and projects towards stable research infrastructures happening in many countries. The Parties advocate cooperation and common activities among Research Infrastructures that have already achieved a high internal organization and legal structure, but also exchange of experience with, and support for networks that have only recently initiated this process.

Article 3. Activities

The above-mentioned goals will be accomplished by undertaking the following activities.

The Parties:

- 3.1 support the development of a hierarchical system of essential variables for ecological observations;
- 3.2 support coherent standards with sufficient, purposeful degrees of freedom;
- 3.3 commit to the registration of their own sites in the DEIMS-SDR (strictly limited to the generic site registration feature, which is also the adopted GEO pilot registry of in-situ observation sites);
- 3.4 will implement open data policies as emphasized by GEO, and will harmonize their respective data access in order to facilitate ecological science through seamless data access;
- 3.5 will increase their data interoperability through common informatics, such as, metadata cataloguing and data citation approaches;
- 3.6 support existing global data efforts (e.g., RDA, FLUXNET);
- 3.7 will support each other and emerging infrastructures in capacity-building and human resource management;
- 3.8 will develop a governance structure for the process towards a global ecosystem research infrastructure including common data policies, intellectual property rights, procedures for common scientific publications and internal communication.

Article 4. Implementation and Reporting

The implementation of the practical actions to achieve the goals reported in Article 3 will be defined with specific action plans that are discussed and defined by the technical and scientific bodies involved in the different research infrastructures.

The parties agree to report individually on their actions annually and to compile a common annual report based on this information with rotational responsibility for the compilation of the overall report.

Article 5. Funding

This MoU is neither a fiscal nor funding document. This MoU does not commit any funding or resource obligation. All Parties enter this MoU with their own capacities and resources. Any activity involving reimbursement or contribution of funds between the Parties to this MoU will be handled separately, outside this MoU, and in accordance with applicable laws, regulations and procedures. Such activities will be part of separate agreements detailing the specific activities between the Parties.

Article 6. Entry into force and duration

- 6.1 This MoU shall enter into force on the date of its signature by the last Party and will have effect for a period of four (4) years from the said date. This MoU shall be renewed automatically for a new four (4)-year period under the same conditions, unless written notification of the contrary is sent by one of the Parties and received by the other Parties at least three (3) months before the expiration date of the four (4)-year period.
- 6.2 Parties may terminate from MoU at any time upon three (3) months prior written notice to the other Parties.
- 6.3 A Party can withdraw at any time from this MoU by giving written notification, as per clause 6.2, to the other Parties. The withdrawal shall take effect upon expiration of three (3) months from the date of receipt by all the Parties of the notification of withdrawal.

- 6.4 A Research Infrastructure wishing to join this MoU can do so by notifying their application to one of the Parties. The parties have three (3) months from the date of application to notify in response whether the application is accepted or not. Any accepted new Party enjoys all rights and obligations contained in this MoU.
- 6.5 The Parties shall jointly evaluate the implementation of this MoU after it has been in force for three (3) years. On the basis of this evaluation, the Parties may make written modifications in order to better fulfil the purpose of this MoU, based on the agreement and acceptance of all conditions by all Parties (not concurrence).

Article 7. Miscellaneous

- 7.1 The Parties expressly acknowledge and accept that this MoU merely constitutes a statement of their mutual intentions without any intention to effect legal relations among them. Further, that its provisions are entirely voluntary and do not create any binding commitments or obligations on any Party, or in favor of any third parties.
- 7.2 In no event shall a Party be liable to another Party for any direct, indirect, incidental, special or consequential damages arising out of performance or failure to perform in accordance with the terms of this MoU, including lost profits, lost revenues, loss of the use of equipment or facilities, or for substitute equipment or facilities.
- 7.3 No Party shall use the names, trademarks or logos of the other Parties nor the names of any of the employees or staff of the other Parties in any commercial advertisement or similar used to promote or sell products or any news release without the prior written approval of the other Party.
- 7.4 This MoU in no way restricts the Parties from participating in similar activities with other public or private agencies, organizations and individuals.
- 7.5 Modifications within the scope of this MoU, including this clause 7.5, shall be made by mutual consent of the Parties in writing.

Article 8. Contact personnel

Name and country/region of the Infrastructure	Contact personnel, Title	Legal Address
Chinese Ecosystem Research Network (CERN), China,		
Integrated Carbon Observation System – European Research Infrastructure Consortium (ICOS ERIC), Europe	<p>Werner L. Kutsch, Director General, ICOS ERIC</p> <p>Emmanuel Salmon, Head of Unit International Cooperation, ICOS ERIC Head Office,</p> <p>Dario Papale, Director of ICOS Ecosystem Thematic Centre</p>	<p>ICOS ERIC Head Office Erik Palménin aukio 1, FI-00560 Helsinki, Finland Phone: +358 50 4484598 Email: werner.kutsch@icos-ri.eu Web: www.icos-ri.eu</p> <p>University of Tuscia Department for innovation in biological, agro-food and forest systems (DIBAF) Largo dell'Università - Blocco D 01100 Viterbo Italy Phone: +39 0761 357044</p>
Integrated European Long-term Ecosystem, Critical Zone and Socio-Ecological Research Infrastructure (eLTER RI)	<p>Michael Mirtl, Coordinator of the eLTER ESFRI process and Chairman LTER-Europe michael.mirtl@umweltbundesamt.at</p> <p>Jaana Bäck, eLTER ESFRI Overall Planning team jaana.back@helsinki.fi</p>	
National Ecological Observatory Network (NEON), USA,	<p>Sharon Collinge, Observatory Director, scollinge@battelleecology.org</p> <p>Rick Farnsworth, Project Manager, rfarnsworth@battelleecology.org</p>	<p>1685 38th St Boulder, Colorado, USA 80301</p>

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The Director, Research Partnerships
The University of Queensland QLD 4072 Australia
Telephone +61 7 3365 3559

**European long-term ecosystem, critical zone and socio-ecological systems research infrastructure
PLUS**

Article 9. Signatures

Those individuals whose signatures appear below hereby certify that they are authorized to sign on behalf of the respective Parties to this MoU. This MoU will be executed in a fashion that each Party will receive one document with original signatures by all.